
Farm machinery

Hydrotillers for wetland ricefields

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The IRRI Hydrotiller is a semifloating rototiller designed to puddle and level soil and to incorporate residues, weeds, or green manure in waterlogged or submerged ricefields. Two models—1.0 m working width (requiring 7-10 hp engine) and 0.8 m working width (requiring 5-6 hp)—are now in commercial production in Southeast Asia.

IRRI has used these Hydrotillers on its research farm field plots and seed increase areas. Advantages are as follows:

- High maneuverability, for speedy puddling and land preparation.
- Capable of working in areas inaccessible to wheeled tractors or water buffalo.
- The entire area of plot or farm field parcel is worked over because the machine cultivates to the edges of bunds, trims edges and corners, and controls and incorporates weeds.
- Two passes at right angles can prepare well-soaked fields or plots for transplanting or direct seeding, without plowing and harrowing.

New IRRI hydrotiller (1.0 m working width) being used to incorporate stubbles in a puddled ricefield.

The 0.8-m Hydrotiller is small enough to be carried by two people. It is maneuverable enough to work in very small plot areas, even as small as 10 m². The regular Hydrotiller can work up to 2 ha with two passes in an 8-h day. It can incorporate *Sesbania rostrata* up to 1.5 m tall (the 0.8-m Hydrotiller cannot work tall green crops or heavy weeds). The twin hulls of the hydrotillers leave no permanent trails, and normal transplant-

ing or direct seeding operations can follow shortly after working with the machines.

Costs in the Philippines are around US\$1300 for the 1.0-m Hydrotiller, including 10-hp gasoline engine, and \$700 for the 0.8-m Mini Hydrotiller, including 5-hp engine with half-speed power takeoff. Blueprints are available free to potential manufacturers from IRRI's Agricultural Engineering Division. ■

ENVIRONMENT

Meteorological aspects of wet season rice cultivation in Sunderbans region, India

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We used three dual-purpose volumetric type rectangular metallic lysimeters (1.2 × 1.2 × 0.90 m) sunk in the middle of well-exposed fields to record crop data.

Daily meteorological data of weeks 30-43 for 6 yr 1982-88 were collected from the CSSRI meteorological observatory at 88°40' E longitude, 22°15' N latitude, and 3 m altitude.

Local improved, salt-resistant, waterlogging-tolerant varieties CSR4 and CR6 were planted in the lysimeter at 15 × 15-cm spacing during the wet seasons. Abstracted mean weekly values of rainfall (R), pan evaporation (PE), lysimetric evapotranspiration [ET(L)], and calculated crop coefficient (Ckp) were recorded Jul-Oct (Table 1).

Weekly PE ranged from 25 mm (Oct) to 31 mm (Aug). ET(L) ranged from 29 mm (Jul) to 39 mm (Oct). Based on ET/PE, Ckp ranged from 1.08 (Jul) to 1.57 (Oct), with an average of 1.30 for the season.

Observed ET(L) was compared with computed potential evapotranspiration (PET) (unadjusted/grass reference/alfalfa reference) by nine empirical methods: Blaney-Criddle (2), Christiansen Default Option, Hargreaves, Jensen-Haise, Turc, Modified Penman, Radiation, and Thornthwaite (Table 1). Coefficient of

variation (CV) ranged from 5.7% (Blaney-Criddle) to 43% (Turc), with an average of 17.3%. Observed ET(L) gave a CV of 17.4%. Observed ET(L) was at par with computed PET values by the Blaney-Criddle, Jensen-Haise, and Turc methods.

ET(L) was at par with PET by Modified Penman and EV or PET by Christiansen Default Option, but computation through these methods requires weather data not commonly available at all agrostations.

We observed that ET(L) had a close relationship with the increasing crop period (weeks 1-14) and produced the relationship $ET(L) = 30.6224 + 0.6224 W$ ($r = 0.411^{**}$ at 82 df). Regression relationships between computed PET (X variable) and observed ET (Y variable) were also established (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Abstracted mean of rainfall, pan evaporation, lysimetric evapotranspiration, and crop coefficient for Sunderbans, India, 1982-88.

Item ^a	Weekly average (mm)				Weekly average for season	CV (%)
	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct		
Rainfall	91	80	54	20	55	117.7
PE	27	31	30	25	28	17.5
ET(L)	29	33	37	39	35	17.4
CkP	1.08	1.14	1.29	1.57	1.30	17.4
Ev (Blaney-Criddle, 1950)	45	47	45	41	44	5.7
Ev (Christiansen Default Option, 1968)	46	38	38	39	39	19.0
ETO (Hargreaves 1985)	27	28	26	26	27	9.6
ETO (Blaney-Criddle, 1977)	59	66	66	72	66	12.4
ETO (Blaney-Criddle, 1950)	58	58	49	37	49	18.4
ETO (Radiation)	40	45	43	45	43	17.2
ETr (Jensen-Haise, 1963)	29	34	34	34	33	18.3
PET (Modified Penman)	36	38	36	32	35	16.0
PET (Christiansen Default Option, 1968)	60	47	42	35	46	24.6
PET (Turc 1960)	26	41	48	69	46	43.5
PET (Thornthwaite)	40	41	39	32	38	19.0

^aPE = pan evaporation, ET(L) = evapotranspiration (lysimetric), Ev = evaporation equivalent to potential pan evaporation, ETO = grass reference potential evapotranspiration, ETr = alfalfa reference potential evapotranspiration.

Table 2. Regression relationships between computed potential evapotranspiration and observed lysimetric evapotranspiration.^a

Method	Relationship	Correlation coefficient
Blaney-Criddle (1950)	: $ET(L) = \text{Exp}(4.8193 - 0.0205 * EV)$	$R = 0.587^*$
Jensen-Haise	: $ET(L) = 1.4834 * ET - 14.2668$	$R = 0.782^{**}$
Turc	: $ET(L) = \text{Exp}(2.3415 + 0.3155 \text{ Log PET})$	$R = 0.796^{**}$
Blaney-Criddle (1977)	: $ET(L) = \text{Exp}(-2.4723 + 1.4353 \text{ Log ETr})$	$R = 0.763^{**}$
Blaney-Criddle (1950)	: $ET(L) = \text{Exp}(3.9608 - 0.0081 ETO)$	$R = 0.572^*$

^aData for weeks 30-43 for 1982-88. * = significant at the 5% level, ** = significant at the 1% level.

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Intensive Weed Management Course at Oregon State University

The International Plant Protection Center at Oregon State University (USA) will conduct an intensive 3-wk, "hands-on" Weed Management Strategies short course 8-26 Jul 1991. The course emphasizes appropriate research strategies and methods for developing countries and is specifically designed for specialists in agriculture.

A free descriptive brochure is available from WMS91 Course, International Plant Protection Center, Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR 97331-3904/USA.

Environmental studies directory

The *1990 Directory of Country Environmental Studies* is now available from the World Resources Institute's Center for

International Development and Environment.

The book is a desk-top guide to environmental assessments, profiles, and strategies completed within the last 10 yr or currently under way. The annotated bibliography presents key information about the content and availability of more than 240 studies on environmental and natural resource conditions in developing countries.

Environmental studies featured cover biological diversity, forestry, natural resources, environmental quality, infrastructure, natural disasters, land-forms and use, oceans and coasts, pollution, energy, soil, and water—and their links to economic development. The Directory covers 110 countries in Africa, Central and South America, the Caribbean, Asia, and Oceania, as well as selected multinational and subnational regions.

A companion IBM-compatible diskette of the data base is also available.

For purchasing information, write CIDE Publications, 1709 New York Ave., NW, 7th floor, Washington, D.C. 20006, USA.

New IIRI publications

Program report for 1989
Phosphorus requirements for sustainable agriculture in Asia and Oceania
Rice: then and now, by R.E. Huke and E.H. Huke
Index of varieties, cultivars, and lines, IRRN Vol. 1, 1976-Vol. 12, 1987
Sharing innovation: global perspectives on food, agriculture, and rural development. Copublished by the Smithsonian Institution Press and IIRI